

Artificial Pancreas under stable MPC: including the Physical Activity effect

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Abstract: This work presents the application of Model Predictive Control (MPC) for the control of blood glucose concentration in patients with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM). The main novelty of the algorithm is the inclusion of physical activity effects, i.e. one of the main critical aspects of the disease. The glyceemic control is based on a physiological individualized long-term compartmental model. Leveraging on this model, the algorithm is able to control glycemia by performing prediction and estimation of patient's next states, employing disturbance observers to compensate plant-model mismatches. The overall performance is tested in a cohort of in-silico patients from the FDA-approved UVA/Padova simulator.

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I. Introduction

Type 1 diabetes (T1D) is a chronic disease that is mainly diagnosed in childhood and adolescent patients and is characterized by a lack of insulin production. It requires lifelong treatments that affect patients' quality of life. Nowadays, the most advanced technology used to facilitate its management is the artificial pancreas (AP) system, a hybrid closed loop (HCL) system based on a set of different devices whose purpose is to improve diabetes management by combining automatic basal insulin delivery with manual boluses during meals. AP systems are characterized by the Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM, i.e., the sensor that records glucose at the interstitial level every few minutes), the insulin pump (i.e., the actuator, which can deliver variable insulin into the subcutaneous tissue), and the control algorithm (i.e., the controller, which calculates the amount of insulin to be delivered). Among those available, Model Predictive Control (MPC) is the most widely used. MPC is a control method that uses a dynamic model to predict the behavior of a system and optimizes these predictions to produce the best control move at any given time. In the case of diabetes, the dynamic model represents the trend of blood glucose (BG) over time as a function of various external factors (disturbances). However, most of them are particularly challenging to model, because it is not clear how they affect glucose absorption. Among these, physical activity (PA) is one of the most challenging, prompting glucose consumption according to the intensity and the duration of the exercise. The controller, which has a single control action (i.e., insulin injection) that induces glucose consumption, must therefore consider the effect of PA, to avoid severe conditions of hypoglycemia ($BG < 70 \text{ mg/dL}$). Here a model of glucose-insulin regulation that accounts for the effects of the exercise on glucose

metabolism is presented, by means of a new subsystem that extends the work in [1]. This is then used into a MPC, considering the scenarios of Programmed and Non-Programmed PA. The control objective is to drive BG levels to the euglycemic range (70-180 mg/dL), while fulfilling the input and state constraints.

I.1. The model

The assumptions of this work are as follows:

Assumption 1: Glycemia evolution is described by a single compartment model.

$$\frac{dG(t)}{dt} = \theta_0 - \theta_1 G(t) - \theta_2 Q_i(t) + \theta_3 Q_g(t) - \theta_6 Q_p(t)$$

Assumption 2: Insulin, Meal and Physical Activity effects are delayed by a two compartmental model structure.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dQ_i(t)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\theta_4} Q_i(t) + \frac{1}{\theta_4} Q_{i_{sub}}(t) \\ \frac{dQ_{i_{sub}}(t)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\theta_4} Q_{i_{sub}}(t) + \frac{1}{\theta_4} u(t) \end{cases} \quad \text{Insulin Subsystem}$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dQ_g(t)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\theta_5} Q_g(t) + \frac{1}{\theta_5} Q_{sto}(t) \\ \frac{dQ_{sto}(t)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\theta_5} Q_{sto}(t) + \frac{1}{\theta_5} r(t) \end{cases} \quad \text{Meal Subsystem}$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dQ_p(t)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\theta_7} Q_p(t) + \frac{1}{\theta_7} Q_{p_{sub}}(t) \\ \frac{dQ_{p_{sub}}(t)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\theta_7} Q_{p_{sub}}(t) + \frac{1}{\theta_7} p(t) \end{cases} \quad \text{PA Subsystem}$$

In these equations $G(t)$ is the glycemia to be controlled, $u(t)$ is the insulin, i.e. the control action, while $r(t)$ is the CHO (carbohydrates amount) in a meal and $p(t)$ is the

Figure 1 Comparison between Programmed PA (blue, left) and Non programmed PA (red, right) scenarios.

exercise intensity. The dynamics of the model between the compartments are described by the rate parameters θ_i .

I.II. Affine State Space Model

According to control purposes, the following affine continuous-time state space model is considered:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}(t) &= Ax(t) + B_u u(t) + B_r r(t) + B_p p(t) + E \\ y(t) &= Cx(t)\end{aligned}$$

II. Material and methods

II.I. Parameter Identification

Parameters θ_i have been identified by means of the following regularized-least square method (RLS), through the MATLAB *fmincon* routine.

$$V_N(\theta) = \frac{\|y(k) - \hat{y}(k)\|^2}{\|y(k) - \bar{y}(k)\|^2} + \theta^0 \alpha \theta^0'$$

The regularization term, $\theta^0 \alpha \theta^0'$, is devoted to steer the identified parameters closed to their physiological values, to maintain model plausibility.

II.II. MPC design

Figure 2 Control scheme

The optimization problem to be solved at the current time k by the MPC on the control horizon N is given by:

$$\min_{u, u_a, x_a} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \|Cx(j) - Cx_a\|_Q^2 + \|u(j) - u_a\|_R^2 + \sum_{j=0}^N \|\delta_j\|_\phi^2$$

s. t.

$$x(0) = \hat{x}$$

$$x(j+1) = A^d x(j) + B_u^d u(j) + B_r^d r(j) + B_p^d p(j) + E^d$$

$$u(j) \in U$$

$$|\tilde{C}x(j)| \leq \tilde{C}X(k) + \delta_j \quad \delta_j \geq 0$$

$$\tilde{C}x(N) = x_a = \tilde{C}A^d x_a + \tilde{C}B^d u_a + \tilde{C}E^d$$

III. Results and discussion

The performance of the MPC under two different PA scenarios has been assessed utilizing the FDA-approved UVA/Padova simulator [2], considering exercise as in [3], with a virtual population of 10 adult patients. Figure 1 shows the controlled glycemia evolution according to different types of exercise (varying both in intensity and duration). The overall application seems promising in terms of controlling the disease in virtual patients. Table 1 shows the different median values for the overall cohort of the time spent in the different BG ranges. Notice that no hypoglycemia events arised in all the 7-day of simulations.

[%time]	Progr. PA	Unprogr. PA
T1TR [70, 140]	64.483 [58.1, 64.9]	63.877 [58.7, 66.5]
T1R [70, 180]	85.676 [83.2, 91.7]	85.636 [83.6, 92.1]
Gm > 180	13.883 [8.2, 16.2]	13.223 [7.1, 14.8]
Gm > 250	0.000 [0.0, 0.0]	0.000 [0.0, 0.0]
Gm < 70	0.000 [0.0, 0.9]	0.947 [0.0, 1.9]
Gm < 54	0.000 [0.0, 0.3]	0.000 [0.0, 0.5]

Table 1 Performance of the controller during the 7-days scenario described as *median [25th, 75th]*.

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